

Insights of Rice Cake Vendors on Community-based tourism (CBT) in Naujan, Oriental Mindoro: Basis for a Management Extension Program

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10539050>

Published Date: 20-January-2024

Abstract: Rice cake vendors living in Pinagsabangan II, Naujan, Philippines, hold a potential key to community-based tourism (CBT). Although a formal understanding of CBT is in its infancy, positive visitor interactions and aspirations for community development suggest exciting possibilities. At the heart of their success are rice cakes, *bibingka* in local terms, beloved cultural product and a cornerstone of memorable tourist encounters. Qualitative interviews with six key informants revealed the challenges they face: lean times, competition, weather, security concerns, and other external factors. Government interventions such as training, promotion, and financial support have been implemented, but gaps in effectiveness need to be addressed. The proposed management extension program of the study aims to address these concerns and unlock the full potential of CBT. Focused on CBT awareness, capacity building, vendor partnerships, and government collaboration, the program seeks to develop a sustainable, inclusive model of tourism that benefits the local community. Ultimately, the tourist experiences will be reinvented using the existing legacy of Pinagsabangan II - its beloved rice cakes.

Keywords: community-based tourism, insights, management extension program, rice cake.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tourism is an important pillar of the economy of many countries and localities around the world [1]. [2] noted that the industry uses the community as a resource, sells it as a product, and in the process, affects the lives of everyone. Communities are sometimes the drivers of why tourists want to travel to the destination because they want to experience their way of life. A concept known as community-based tourism (CBT) has been introduced to avoid rapid tourism development without an understanding of the local economy and the quality of local livelihoods [2]. This concept suggests that tourism development projects should be managed and owned by the community, for the community, to enable visitors to increase their awareness and learn about the community and the locals' ways of life.

The Provincial Tourism Code of Oriental Mindoro or the Provincial Ordinance No. 139-2022 sets a frame of reference for utilizing tourism as a means for the province's sustainable growth and development, investment and employment, and cultural affirmation. To ensure sustainability in development plans, the code encourages local government units to formulate, implement, and update Local Tourism Development Plans and Local Cultural Development Plans because of their evolving needs and capabilities, and the demands of the international and domestic tourism market. The Provincial Tourism Code does not only provide for policies for sustainable tourism but also responsible tourism that integrates the protection of Oriental Mindoro's biodiversity, marine protected areas, ecotourism destinations, farm tourism sites, and historical and heritage zones as well as the capacitation or Community-based Sustainable Tourism Organizations (CBSTOs) and other associations who manage them. It is a clear manifestation that the province urges for a sustainable organization that will start within the community.

This study was conducted to assess the CBT potential in the community of Pinagsabangan II, (other term is Curva) Naujan. The municipality of Naujan is a 1st class and the largest municipality in the province of Oriental Mindoro, Philippines. The

province is an island located under the MIMAROPA region in Luzon, about 140 kilometres (87 mi) southwest of Manila, the capital of the country. The province is home to nature-based tourism sites like white sand beaches, rivers, waterfalls, museums, hiking spots, festivals, and food hubs.

The rice cake (bibingka in local terms) is not just a source of income for the community vendors in Naujan, Oriental Mindoro, but more importantly, an expression of their love for their local culture and lifelong way of living, which is ultimately the by-product of a formalized and potential community-based tourism product. A total of twenty rice cake vendors are available up to this day. They are composed of those who own stalls built just near the nautical highway, and some are peddlers serving this native delicacy for almost twenty years. The rice cake is a food sold in different provinces all over the Philippines, rice cake vendors in Naujan have these sold 365 days a year and some offer it 24/7. Although, it has been sold and offered for over two decades already, there is no current and registered rice cake vendor's association or organization built to manage its enterprise.

FIGURE I: RICE CAKE OF NAUJAN, ORIENTAL MINDORO

Source: Official Facebook page of Oriental Mindoro Provincial Tourism Office
<https://www.facebook.com/share/zYHLAduRDpbn1j7Y/?mibextid=WC7FNe>

Limelight for rice cake should be timely given for the community to continuously flourish and develop their CBT and uplift their livelihood. That is why this study tried to fill the necessity to know the perception of rice cake vendors in supporting community development changes through embracing a niche of tourism which is CBT. The researcher saw that this was applicable in the chosen locale since there was an existing product that is developed and utilized by the community members which is rice cake though there is a concurring need to formalize it having known that most of the raw materials and ingredients are highly sourced within the community. This was also communicated and supported by the Provincial Tourism Office (PTO) which according to them, the community organization should be addressed first. To attend to that, community tourism perception, insights, experiences as well as their challenges in connection with their rice cake business should be determined first. Challenges seen by the community may be a hindrance to community participation. This concept is supported by [3] who emphasized that community-based tourism without active "community" participation is not consistent with the basic concept and principles of CBT. Through determining these, stakeholders may know the extensive assistance that can be aided to the community which may help them holistically.

This study emphasized answering the following:

- 1) What is the rice cake vendor's idea of tourism?
- 2) What are their memorable interactions and experiences with tourists?
- 3) What is the relationship between CBT and the rice cake business?
- 4) What are the LGU and provincial government's interventions to the rice cake vendors?
- 5) What are the challenges face by rice cake vendors in their business?

This study employed a qualitative approach through personal interviews with six key informants (rice cake vendors) The study was conducted from September-November 2023. The questions administered during the interview were translated into local language to encourage in-depth and free expression from the respondents.

Respondents who participated in the interviews were informed in advance and provided consent for the recording of the sessions for documentation purposes. Acknowledgment was made regarding the presence of physical noise, such as vehicle sounds, during the interviews to ensure that it did not impact the interviewees' responses. The recorded interviews were transcribed using an online application and subsequently verified through private playback.

This study served as the basis for a proposed community management extension program in support of the existing provincial and local interventions.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Respondents of the Study

TABLE I: PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Socio-Demographic Profile of Rice Cake Vendors						
Respondents	Age	Gender	Educational Attainment	Monthly Gross Income	Years of residency in the community	Years of engagement in the rice cake business
R1	51	F	High School Graduate	30,000.00	50 yrs	6 yrs
R2	37	F	College Graduate	10,500.00	37 yrs	10 yrs
R3	46	F	College Graduate	45,000.00	46 yrs	19 yrs
R4	52	F	High School Graduate	4,000.00	52 yrs	18 yrs
R5	53	F	High School Graduate	30,000.00	53 yrs	18 yrs
R6	45	F	High School Undergraduate	24,000.00	24 yrs	10 yrs

TABLE I shows the profile of the key informants during the qualitative interview. It presents the age, gender, educational attainment, monthly gross income, years of residency, and most importantly the years of engagement in the rice cake business. It is essential to consider the socio-demographic profile of the respondents as it can provide valuable considerations into their perception of the concept of CBT.

B. Insights of the rice cake vendors on the concept of tourism and CBT

From the personal interviews with six (6) rice cake vendors, the following concepts were acquired and thematized according to the notions that emerged. The following themes emerged:

1. Knowledge of Tourism

The researcher tried to gauge the ideas of the rice cake vendors on the concept of tourism as this is essential before introducing niche like CBT. The below themes present were acquired.

Tourism as an activity

Respondent 1 said, *"This is for beautifying and enhancing our community by elevating our resorts. Similar to ours, rice cake, for improvement, for tourists to see how rice cake is made here in Pinagsabangan II. And it is visited by travelers, by tourists who come here to Curva.*

Additionally, according to Respondent 2, *"Tourism. When we talk about tourism, it's the visitation or journey of people to explore what we have in our area. They want to experience or taste it. That's it. Something like that. Furthermore, Respondent 3 asserted that "Tourism, for me, is the overall engagement of people in the community to provide them with livelihood or business opportunities".*

Tourism as individuals

Meanwhile, the rest of the respondents viewed tourism as officers or individuals involved rather than an activity. Respondent 4 said, *"Tourism is what introduces us to rice cake, so they can introduce themselves to us and prosper. Similarly, Respondent 5 said "To maintain a sense of order, to have appealing packaging, and to ensure proper cooking." Furthermore, Respondent 6 said "Sometimes, when I hear about it, it makes me think that maybe one day, I'll be the one being helped by them. Something like that."*

Three of the respondents viewed tourism as an activity that includes the visitation of non-residents to their community to experience places or food. The knowledge of tourism among the respondents might differ because of how it has impacted them or the way they have experienced the concept in their everyday lives. Rice cake vendors are engrossed in their daily business operations, pondering how their enterprise will flourish and their levels of observance may vary from one another regarding the concept of tourism or the activity itself.

According to study cited by [4], business-specific context influences residents' perceptions and attitudes. For instance, residents in direct businesses with continuous contact with tourists have different perceptions of tourism than those with no contact with tourists. That is why this study has involved asking its respondents about their perception of the general concept of tourism to further assess how familiar they are with its nature, which will be more beneficial for tourists in the times to come. It can somehow be affected also by the level of education of the respondents. The study by [5] found that highly educated and employed residents perceive more negative impacts of tourism on their quality of life than others.

2. Memorable Interaction and Experiences with Tourists

Rice cake is part of the unique tourist experience.

Respondents are also asked to share their memorable experiences and interactions with customers during their rice cake business operations about the tourism activity in the area.

Respondent 1 mentioned, *"When they arrive, they see how the rice cake is cooked, they witness the process... how is it done, what is the first step? It starts with rice soaked and mixed with various ingredients that add flavor—things like eggs, milk, and more, depending on the one preparing it. I won't mention all the ingredients, but that's how we are known, at Curva"*.

Likewise, respondent 2 stated that *"In other words, they say that every time they return to Mindoro, it's a must for them to pass by our barangay to buy rice cake."* Respondent 3 emphasized, *"What I can say about that is when they buy from me, they mention that the rice cake is delicious, even the ginger tea, which we give for free to our customers"*.

Additionally, respondent 4 delightedly mentioned that *"They are delighted since it's the first time, they've tasted free ginger tea and rice cake"*.

Rice cake business as a social opportunity

Respondent 6 revealed, *"I am pleased because I realize that I can interact with people of diverse personalities, and it is through this that I get to know their characters. It seems like they see me as part of the family"*.

Constructive feedback

According to respondent 5, *"What I can say is that the visitors here who buy rice cake only have one thing to say, and that is they hope for better packaging and for the rice cake to have different flavors"*.

According to the respondents when asked about their memorable interactions and experiences as shown in TABLE III, rice cake is part of the tourists' experience. It became both a tangible and intangible tourism product as it not only provides a means to wipe away traveler's hunger but also a sense of relief as it is a comfort food. This is a perfect opportunity for the stakeholders to maximize the already acquired capital of the community, rice cake, in reinventing the traveler's experience. Rice cake vendors appreciate how they are aided with income and economic sustainability through the opportunity to encounter and accept diversity from their customers. Other customers who had the chance to buy rice cake had deep concerns over its marketability and suggested forward-thinking inputs to further improve the product.

Three categories of development strategies would help materialize the objectives of the province. First, reinventing Oriental Mindoro as a tourism destination for outdoor recreation and culture in 2027. Second, creating a strong position for Oriental Mindoro in the Philippine Domestic Tourism Market by 2027; Third, strengthening the capacity of the different local tourism offices of Oriental Mindoro to manage tourism and meet the demands of the tourism industry by 2027 [6]. The three categories of development strategies that would help materialize the mentioned objectives are: reinventing the traveller's experience, focusing on the domestic tourism market, and strengthening LGU's role in tourism development. The themes acquired in the interview on rice cake vendor's memorable interaction signifies that it has been added to the informal brand of the province in reinventing tourists' experience.

3. Relationship Between CBT and the Rice Cake business

Respondents are also asked on what is their idea regarding the relationship between CBT and their Rice cake business.

Exposure of the community through Rice cake

Respondent 1 mentioned *"Sometimes, there's this celebrity who visited our bibingkahan (rice cake shop) there, along with our colleagues. I can't remember the name of that child who cooked the rice cake. It seems like he was genuinely delighted to cook the rice cake. This means we are gaining recognition and boosting tourism in Curva. They even took pictures and videos there to show tourists how to cook rice cake."*

Additionally, respondent 2 mentioned *"It's great because aside from increasing our income, we also gained new friends."* In support of the brand exposure, respondent 3 mentioned that *"When they've tasted rice cake, they'll keep coming back for*

it.” Furthermore, respondent 6 affirmed *“Isn't it the same for you? If you smell rice cake every day, it becomes a bit tiresome. So, it's good to have tourism.”*

Respondents are appreciative of the connections and exposure that they gained from their engagement in the rice cake business noting that they have expanded their horizons as entrepreneurs and the brand of rice cake as it ensures positive exposure to the community. Understandably, they have limited knowledge of CBT which resulted in only three of them having an idea about it.

The industry uses the community as a resource, sells it as a product, and in the process, affects the lives of everyone [2]. Communities are sometimes the drivers of why tourists want to travel to the destination because they want to experience their way of life. Part of the assets of Pinagsabangan II is their rice cake. Based on the findings, their engagement in the rice cake business has paved them to gain connections and increase their exposure that will eventually benefit the community.

4. LGU and provincial government's intervention in the rice cake business

Rice cake vendors were also asked on what were the past interventions made by the provincial and local government and below were the themes that emerged.

Training Programs

As much as the rice cake vendors are concerned, they have delineated various training programs provided through the initiative of the LGU.

Respondent 1 mentioned that *“When we had something like a TESDA (Technical Education and Skills Development Authority) training on how to package and elevate Curva's rice cake.”* Respondent 4 revealed that they were also provided with trainings on innovation such as putting different flavors in their rice cake, *“Oh, yes. I can apply that to my rice cake. That's what we apply, putting different flavors. Then, I apply it when making special rice cake, when there's an order, that's what I include. It's okay. The training they conducted for us is also beneficial.”*

Respondent 5 also added, *“Regarding the flavor and packaging, for now, we haven't implemented it yet because it's too costly for us to do so. And for things like putting it in a box, it's somewhat, for people like us, we lack funds, we still can't afford to do that.”*

When asked about trainings that were not provided and wished to receive, respondent 4 mentioned that, *“Some things, we just need to know the expiration date. It hasn't been trained to us yet. Because that's necessary, right? That's what we're saying. For hours. We're not sure. There should be someone who will really teach and provide training on the due date or how long the rice cake will expire. Because no one has trained us on that yet. Just flavors. They haven't informed us about when it will expire).* This is also expressed by respondent 6, *“Because I really want to know the rice cake's shelf life, how many days before it goes stale.”*

Financial Support

For any business organization, whether it be a formal or an informal one, financial support is necessary especially those that will come from its stakeholders like the government.

Respondent 1 mentioned that *“That time, we had your LSFI (Livelihood Settlement Fund Initiative, a project of the Department of Social Welfare and Development), and we were given financial assistance for those who make rice cake. We were provided with capital, and we were given tools to help us improve.”* This has been added by respondent 2 who stated that, *“The previous time when they provided funding for those who make rice cake.”* Furthermore, respondent 4 mentioned that *“They provided us with a small capital. We then grew that, although not excessively. We expanded it, and until now, there are still some tools remaining. But we continue to use them up to this day, with that initial small capital. We haven't received any additional funding since then.”* Likewise, respondent 5 mentioned, *“They are one of those who provided us with funding. And they will give again to continue improving and enhancing those who make rice cake.”*

Promotion

Rice cake vendors are entrepreneurs in themselves. They have their duties of promoting their business to the full extent of reaching a wide array of customers. However, for others, it can be bothersome because they are also looking after the overall operations such as making sure that their product is always available, raw materials are accessible and it will be sold in the best quality possible. LGU has taken some part of promoting their rice cake business and it expressed by the respondents.

Respondent 3 mentioned, *“Through their use of Facebook to promote it in various places.”* Nonetheless, when asked for the LGU's intervention on promotion, respondent 2 revealed, *“It's not that obvious because it seems like we can stand on*

our own even without the endorsement being mentioned. But if there is an endorsement, it's better, of course, for us to be more recognized."

In the context of this study, the goal was to develop a management extension program specifically tailored for rice cake vendors in Naujan. As part of the research process, respondents were queried regarding any interventions or actions undertaken by the Local Government Unit (LGU) on their behalf. The aim was to gather insights into the existing support and assistance provided to the rice cake vendors by the local government. The term "intervention" here refers to any proactive measures, programs, or initiatives implemented by the LGU to address the needs or concerns of the rice cake vendors. This could encompass a range of activities, such as financial support, training programs, infrastructure development, or any other form of assistance aimed at improving the vendors' overall well-being and enhancing their business operations.

The first consideration when preparing for CBT is that the community needs to be assisted in comprehending the mechanisms of tourism as well as the potential impacts before deciding to initiate a tourism operation [7]. Tourism brings some negativities in the community that members might consider not to have it. Additionally, [8] states that CBT suffers because of the lack of financial sustainability which is sometimes due to the absence of business expertise, knowledge among members, and access to the market. This is where the government should step in. Aside from determining the existing community assets like competitive products, community needs assessment should also be effectively done. In that way, the members of the community might receive the intervention that they really need. Given that the LGU and the provincial government in the research area of the study have tangibly provided the rice cake vendors with training programs, and financial and promotional support, the great challenge for them is how to properly equip them to implement these programs sustainably and enable them in nourishing what they receive. That is why this study proposed a management extension program that will hopefully suffice the needs of the rice cake vendors in any way possible.

5. Challenges of Rice cake Vendors

Lean Season

Respondent 1 mentioned, *"It's probably the same with the slow days. Because during slow days, there's Monday. The faster days are Friday, Saturday, Sunday."* Respondent 2 also stated, *"When business is slow, as was the case last September for nearly a month, it becomes extremely challenging. The sales are so slow that the vendor is even incurring costs like paying for our seller."* When asked if the current agreed price for rice cake is enough, respondent 2 mentioned, *"It's okay because there's still income. The problem, however, arises during slow times when we can't sell everything. Then, we still must pay the vendor)."* She also elaborated that given the situation of being in lean season, rice cake vendors might stop in the rice cake business. *"Perhaps, because if it's always slow, there's a possibility that some might stop. So, the numbers of rice cake vendors will decrease. And, if we become fewer, tourists may not visit us anymore."*

Because of the lean season, respondent 3 also stated that spoilage of raw materials is inevitable. *"Similar to the spoilage of rice flour."* And also mentioned, *"There is a solution for that, and that is to have only a small amount of rice flour at a time to avoid spoilage."* Due to their long experience in the business, they also know how to handle unforeseen circumstances like spoilage to avoid costs.

Furthermore, respondent 4 stated when asked what the possible reasons of lean days are, *"Perhaps it's also because of the people's situation. The demand for rice cake, especially now that classes have started, has decreased. Of course, those who used to buy rice cake might now be allocating their budget for their children's needs."* Additionally, respondent 5 also expressed, *"We experienced challenges during the lean season when we were incurring losses. Our sales were not enough to cover. Because we have vendors to pay. That's when we realized the need to expand our offerings, like adding coffee and mami, so that we wouldn't fall short of paying the vendors."* Respondent 6 also expressed, *"When it comes to slow selling of rice cake, that is my problem because how many children do I have? Two from college and one from high school. That's where I earn my daily income."* When asked if she has other source of income, she mentioned, *"None. Only here. So, when I can't sell all and business is slow, I think, 'What now? It gives me a headache thinking about where I'll get money. Tomorrow, it's for the children's transportation fare."*

Competition

Respondent 3 stated, *"Another challenge we face is... In addition to slow days, competition is also a factor."* When asked if that challenge affects the overall CBT in the area, she mentioned, *"Not really, because each one has their own set of regular customers."* Respondent 4 also mentioned competition is also a challenge for them. *"Most customers really go beyond. Wherever they've experienced satisfaction, that's where they stick. Yes, it's also about your customers. If they like it, they'll keep coming back."*

External Challenges like safety and weather condition

Respondent 1 mentioned, *“The earnings from rice cake are slow. Sometimes, when it rains, rice cake doesn't sell well”* She also mentioned Respondent 4 expressed, *“The climate, especially during rainy days.”* Respondent 6 also mentioned that some of her customers are complaining about the weather whenever they choose to dine at their stalls. She said, *“It's hot, and when they stop there, they are behind the vehicle.”*

Respondents are also asked if they are fine with the Rice Cake Food Plaza project that will somehow solve some of the external challenges that they have mentioned like safety and weather conditions. Respondent 1 expressed, *“I hope what Governor mentioned about giving us a terminal for those selling rice cake will come true. The Rice cake Food Plaza.”* She added, *“For us, indeed, it's suggested to create the Bibingka Food Plaza to make it presentable. But perhaps, it's in the discussion among rice cake vendors on how we can improve rice cake here in Curva even more.”* Respondent 6 expressed her hopes that when the time comes that the Rice cake Food Plaza will really push through, advance notices and communication will be given. *“It's okay. As long as it's communicated in advance.”*

Just like all businesses, rice cake vendors are not an exception to fluctuating business operations that affect their sales. Some challenges encountered by rice cake vendors are due to changes in the market's demand conditions as well as their purchase capacity over time. Rice cake stalls are located on the national highway of the municipality of Naujan. Customers while on purchase are just parked in front of the stalls. Some vendors claimed that customers come and go and fewer opt to dine in because of the location. Subsequently, the weather condition is a plus factor in low sales among the rice cake vendors especially during the rainy season.

In connection to the current study, based on the secondary data provided by both the Provincial Tourism Office and the barangay, the Project Brief of proposed Rice cake Food Plaza which outlines the budget for the rice cake makers aim to put the product with the people in the same place provided that this objective will create a safer place for tourists and will eventually improve and reinvent their traveler experience as emphasized in the PTDMP (2022-2027). This is a significant breakthrough for the province and especially the community in trying to formalize the industry of the rice cake vendors as well as the overall industry of local food businesses. The proposed Naujan Rice Cake Food Plaza is composed of stalls, enclosed in one compound with safe parking, comfortable kiosks for eating, restrooms and other amenities for tourists and travelers. This has been brought up by the vendors but as to what is expected, they initially refuse the idea since one of their concerns is the changes with the location. This study has identified the challenges experienced by the rice cake vendors to better understand their insights toward future government interventions.

C. Proposed Management Extension Program

EXTENSION PROPOSAL

I. BASIC INFORMATION

A. Title:	Project SALABAT: Strengthening Advancements, Local Entrepreneurial Awareness Building, and Advancing Community Based Tourism- A Management Extension Program for Naujan Rice cake Vendors
B. Project Leader:	Catherine M. Campo
C. Duration	Year 2024
D. Location	Naujan, Oriental Mindoro
E. Costs	Php 95, 000.00

II- RATIONALE:

Project SALABAT: Strengthening Advancements, Local Entrepreneurial Awareness Building, and Advancing Community-Based Tourism (CBT) to support existing government interventions. "Salabat" as the program title, intends to convey the idea that salabat (ginger tea) is incomplete without rice cake, emphasizing the complementary nature of the two. Similarly, the community's efficiency is contingent on the presence of capital, assets, and possible external assistance.

III- OBJECTIVES:

1. To empower the rice cake vendors as self-sufficient entrepreneurs by providing business management practices to help them sustain and grow their businesses.
2. To enable vendors with a comprehensive understanding of CBT, enabling them to serve as adept and strategic community ambassadors for their businesses.
3. To provide supplemental capability trainings that will help them produce more competitive and innovative products, manpower and practices.

IV- PROGRAM COMPONENTS:

The program components will revolve around the following:

TABLE II: MANAGEMENT EXTENSION PROGRAM COMPONENTS

Component	Extension Activities/ Training Course	Objectives	Persons Involved	Beneficiaries	Duration
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthening Advancements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food Safety and Sanitation Training Product Innovation Training Customer Service Training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhance the overall competency and competitiveness of food entrepreneurs through a comprehensive training program 	LGU-DOT Industry Experts (private or public)	Rice cake vendors	2024
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local Entrepreneurial Awareness Building 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entrepreneurial Mind setting <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal Entrepreneurial Competencies (PEC) Assessment Opportunity Seeking Networking and Relationship Building Risk-taking and Risk Management Organization and Management Seminar and Workshop Financial Literacy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To cultivate various components that contribute to an individual's ability to think and act like an entrepreneur Equip participants with essential organizational and management skills through a seminar and workshop, fostering a deeper understanding of effective leadership, strategic planning, and operational efficiency for enhanced organizational success and sustainability. To empower the rice cake vendors with the knowledge and skills necessary to make informed and effective financial decisions. 	Industry Experts (private or public)	Rice cake vendors	2024
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advancing Community Based Tourism (CBT) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tourism Information Transfer <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nature of Tourism Rice cake as a Tourism Product Environmental Conservation in Tourism Sustainable Tourism Community Participation concept of CBT Seminar workshop on collaborative and inclusive CBT Internal and External Factors of CBT Community-Based Sustainable Tourism Organizations (CBSTOs) Experiential Tourism Seminar and Workshop Filipino Brand of Service Excellence (FBSE) Seminar Training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To increase the awareness of the community to the nature of tourism To assist the community in forming their active and progressive CBSTOs in line with the community vision and aspirations Impart the knowledge of experiential tourism to authenticate visitor's experience To subject the rice cake vendors to FBSE training by the DOT as tourism business frontlines 	LGU-DOT Industry Experts (private or public)	Rice cake vendors	2024

**Budgetary and Gantt charts were not included.*

III. CONCLUSION

Community members are a vulnerable part of the tourism industry. When tourism activities are not planned well, with them and for them, they will be the ones to least enjoy it. Rice cake vendors of Naujan are an integral part of the progressive community. Without them, there would be no CBT product that is being enjoyed today. This study revealed that the rice cake vendors though has differentiated knowledge of tourism and CBT, experiences, and challenges, are willing to accept more interventions as they are very attached to their livelihood. Tourism is a great opportunity for them. To attain sustainability in the community through niches like CBT, stakeholders should come together to attain development goals. The proposed management extension program of the study aims to address the perceived challenges and unlock the full potential of CBT. Focused on CBT awareness, capacity building, vendor partnerships, and government collaboration, the program seeks to develop a sustainable, inclusive model of tourism that benefits the local community. Ultimately, the tourist experiences will be reinvented using the existing legacy of Pinagsabangan II - its beloved rice cakes. Future researchers might consider a total enumeration of respondents whose engaged in the business such as those vendors to gather extensive findings.

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